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Paediatric Social Workers And Child Health In Inpatient And Outpatient Medical Settings

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ABSTRACT

Families of children with serious medical conditions often experience intense hardships that can negatively impact their mental, emotional, social and financial well-being. They may also have difficulty advocating for themselves and their child in a complex and at times confusing medical system. Paediatric Social Workers provide a wide variety of services to assist these families, including but not limited to individual and group counselling, guidance in applying for insurance and other benefits, connections to community resources and support, crisis interventions and facilitating effective communication between patients, families and the larger medical team. One of the primary responsibilities of Paediatric Social Workers or Medical Social Workers is helping young patients and their families cope with the emotional and psychological trauma and strain of dealing with severe illness. Understandably, the greatest challenge faced by families of pediatric patients is the sudden or chronic infirmity of their child. Children who are afflicted with acute or chronic medical problems can experience sudden and/or severe escalations in their condition, which can be deeply stressful for their parents and family. The children with chronic illnesses would be hospitalized frequently for acute issues – such as pneumonia – to which they are more susceptible and for whom it could mean a severe deterioration of their condition or even death. It is during these times that families are in the most need of care coordination, resource attainment, psychoeducation and support. This paper examines the role paediatric social workers play in inpatient and outpatient medical settings and the support and services they render to paediatric patients and their families to improve child health.

Keywords: Paediatric Social Workers, Child Health, Inpatient, Outpatient, Medical Settings

INTRODUCTION

Paediatric Social Workers work in inpatient and outpatient medical settings to support children who are experiencing chronic and/or severe medical conditions. They also work with the families of paediatric patients, providing emotional support, counselling, care coordination, connections to important resources, and help navigating the medical system and communicating with medical teams. Paediatric Social Workers typically work in the paediatric departments of hospitals and medical centers, but may also work at private practices and clinics, community health centers and other settings that provide medical care to children and adolescents.

Job Description at a Glance

- Paediatric Social Workers integrate a child's social and psychological needs into a medical care plan by:
- Providing counselling and support to adjust to illness and grief.
- Providing crisis intervention.
- Assisting with communication between family and medical team.
- Advocating on behalf of the child and family on medical treatment and other services.
- Connecting to community resources and trauma services.
- Participating in discharge planning.

The paediatric social worker's role combines clinical social work duties with medical care coordination and work with vulnerable children and their families. As a result, social work students who want to work in pediatric social work should build strong skills in clinical counseling and therapeutic methods, crisis interventions and management, and caring for children and families experiencing hardships. They should also familiarize themselves with health care systems and actively seek internships in medical (and if possible, paediatric) settings. Pediatric Social Work is a field that requires a great deal of preparation, compassion, skill and resilience. It is not a field for the faint of heart, as it involves holding up and guiding children and their families during some of the most trying and potentially tragic moments in their lives. However, with the rigors and difficulties of this profession come deeply rewarding relationships with patients and colleagues, and the knowledge that one's work has a positive impact on the quality of medical care pediatric patients receive.

Emotional Support and Counselling

Paediatric patients and their families face complex, challenging and at times sad situations. Emotionally, patients and parents are often dealing with the unknown and the ongoing need to maintain hope. They are often confused by medical terminology and differing opinions on treatment plans. Sometimes parents don't want the patient to know what diagnosis they have, to protect them, which can be difficult for the medical team to support. Other times parents tell their children too much information, causing anxiety and fear in the patient. It is difficult at times for the parents to find a middle ground, and of course if the diagnosis is terminal or life limiting – the patient and families are grieving, each in their own way.

During this time of confusion, anxiety and vulnerability, paediatric social workers provide patients and families with compassionate support and short-term counselling. When counselling patients and their families, paediatric social workers may use a number of psychotherapeutic methods, including but not limited to psychosocial assessments, risk assessments, supportive psychotherapy, cognitive behavioral therapy, psychoeducation, and mindfulness-based stress reduction. In addition to providing one-on-one and group counselling, paediatric social workers may also facilitate larger therapeutic groups to promote intra-family communication and support. Shellie Leger, MSW, who worked at Massachusetts General Hospital as a pediatric social worker for six years, told Online MSW Programs: "I supported my patients/families by offering short-term psychotherapy; psycho education regarding their child's illness and the needs of siblings; formation and facilitation of support groups as needed, such as sibling support and family recreation; and grief work."

Guidance and Support in Navigating Medical System

In addition to providing emotional support, paediatric social workers help patients and their families comprehend their situation, the medical system, and what processes and procedures will be involved in the care of their child. Paediatric Social Workers help patients' families find their footing and move forward with the medical team to address their child's condition. Paediatric Social Workers orient families to the large and complex hospital system, and prepare them for what to expect; help them navigate the many different components of the system and ensure they have the necessary resources to be present with their child and active in care.

Paediatric Social Workers can often be a source of stability in an environment of rapid change. “At LPCHS the social worker follows the patient and family throughout the hospitalization. Therefore, should the patient move to the PICU, I follow them on that unit and if they move from the PICU to the med-surg floor, I continue to work with them as their social worker,” Barnhardt explained to Online MSW Programs. “Since LPCHS is a teaching hospital, the medical teams change weekly, which can be difficult for patients and families. As a social worker I remain consistent in the lives of the patient and family, which is often very important to them. If a patient discharges from the hospital and is readmitted to the hospital, I will again follow them throughout their hospitalization.”

Crisis Interventions

Paediatric Social Workers provide support and crisis management services to families experiencing medical emergencies or acute emotional distress in response to their child’s condition. “Many families are in crisis mode and I provide crisis intervention services, which would include general support, resources, referrals to appropriate agencies or services within the hospital, specific steps to follow (like homework), suicide assessments, and even walking parents to the ED for mental health assessments if needed. At times it is important to discuss death, dying, grief and bereavement,” Barnhardt told Online MSW Programs. “Crises were a routine aspect of the work. Because the children were so ill, they would often suffer from ‘codes’ (loss of oxygenation to the body, or cardiac arrest), complications during procedures, and ‘rapid responses’ (immediate need for transfer from acute to intensive care),” Kido told Social Work License Map of her time at LPCHS. “Families would need social workers to provide support, guidance, and information while the medical team was focused on the child and unable to attend to the family.”

In addition to medical crises, personal crises also occur in paediatric medical settings – and social workers are called upon to address these situations. “Families would experience their own crises in the form of panic attacks, dangerously high blood sugars from forgetting their insulin at home, fighting with an ex in the hallway, and being verbally abusive to the medical team, social workers help these families find healthier ways to manage their emotions and situations.” Kido said.

Care Coordination and Treatment Planning with Medical Team

Social Workers coordinate patient care by communicating with and helping to organize all parties that are invested in a patient’s medical treatment. Social Workers discuss patients’ needs with physicians, nurses, medical assistants and other staff during their development of a treatment plan and relay any ongoing concerns that patients’ families have to the team. “I work closely with the medical teams in development of treatment plans,” Deetta Barnhardt, told Online MSW Programs. “The medical teams utilize family centered rounds, multidisciplinary rounds, bedside meetings, care conferences and ongoing direct communication to include social workers in on treatment planning. I have direct access to medical teams through paging them or calling their ASCOM phones.”

Social Workers serve as the point of contact between not only patients’ families and the medical team, but also medical and non-medical teams within the hospital that all collaborate to provide medical care. “LPCHS employed physicians, nurse practitioners, nurses, NAs, case managers, chaplains, child life specialists, financial counsellors, pharmacy techs, nutritionists, patient experience reps, and all colors of administrators, all of whom played their part in the journey of the patient and family,” Kido explained to Social Work License Map. “Social Workers document extensively in the electronic medical record, attend rounds daily, organize care conferences, and are in constant communication with other providers via phone, email, pager, and in person to communicate the issues and needs of the family.”

Through their strong understanding of their clients’ mental and emotional health, as well as their social, cultural and financial circumstances, paediatric social workers help guide other members of the hospital staff in providing sensitive, compassionate and consequently effective care. “This was why obtaining a thorough psychosocial assessment was so important,” Kido noted. “Others were relying on social workers to know how best to interface with the family based on their unique needs and circumstances.”

In addition to communicating with the various teams within the hospital setting on a daily basis, social workers also schedule and facilitate meetings between medical teams and between patient families and medical staff. Leger noted to Online MSW Programs that one of her core responsibilities at Massachusetts General Hospital was “the planning and forming of patient care conferences to assure coordination of care amongst the multidisciplinary teams that served each child/family.” Leger also mentioned the important role that paediatric social workers play in interpreting the at times emotionally charged reactions patients’ families have. “It is not surprising that we are often cultural brokers, being educated and trained to appreciate the cognitive dissonance that ensues when there is a culture clash at play,” she said. “Social Workers are often integral in interpreting behavior of family members and/or patients through the lens of social norms in the context of culture, and carrying this information to the greater team.”

Resource Connections

Paediatric Social Workers are deeply connected to organizations, programme and other resources within and outside of the hospital setting that may be helpful to patients and their families, and actively work to connect their clients to these resources. “I work closely with many community agencies and often make referrals to organizations such as the Family Advocacy Project, Ronald McDonald House, Child Protective Services, TANF/CalWorks, WIC, Public Health Nursing, the Shelter Network, Legal Aid and Make-A-Wish to name a few,” Barnhardt told Online MSW Programs. I also refer patients to services within our hospital including child life, chaplaincy, palliative care and psychology.” Similarly, during her time at LPCHS, Kido told Social Work License Map that “we connected families to external resources, such as food banks, outpatient therapy, and in-home support services, as well as coordinating with external organizations, such as Child Protective Services, probation officers and attorneys/legal aid representatives.” Paediatric Social Workers can also reach out to community resources on behalf of their patients.

Challenges Faced by Paediatric Social Workers

Many paediatric social workers describe their work as both intensely challenging and deeply rewarding; often, the very aspects of their job that are rewarding are the same ones that present the toughest challenges. “It is absolutely rewarding to work with paediatric patients and their families in the hospital setting. Having the opportunity to witness the strength of children’s spirit and innocence is truly a gift, and imparts a sense of awe, respect and inspiration to those in their presence,” Kido told Social Work License Map. “The most rewarding part, however, was also the most devastating. Walking with a family, carrying a tiny piece of their burden as they process, live and grieve the death of their child is something few people have the chance to experience. Although social workers in this position are witnesses to the most palpable, heaviest pain imaginable, in the same moment, they are witness to the strongest love.”

Paediatric Social Workers or Medical Social Workers may also encounter frustrations with the medical system and being unable to thoroughly address their clients’ struggles. “The most challenging aspect of this work was the inherent inability to meet the needs of every family,” Kido said. “Given the number of patients to which we were assigned, the complexity of their lives and illnesses, the scarcity of resources both within and outside the hospital system, and the expectations of the medical teams, there was simply no way to achieve everything I set out to.” When encountering this challenge, paediatric social workers may need to prioritize their tasks according to the severity and urgency of their patients’ needs, and accept the limitations of their own abilities, resources and schedules.

To manage the challenges, paediatric social workers or medical social workers should develop and maintain a strong and consistent self-care plan. During her time as a field instructor, Kido discussed with her student the importance of establishing healthy boundaries between work and personal life. “I encouraged the student under my supervision to set limits for himself and to leave on time whenever possible,” she said. “I recommended being responsive to the needs of the medical team, while setting limits with them as well.”

CONCLUSION

Despite the intense demands and strains of the job, the relationships that paediatric social workers forge with their colleagues and patients can be deeply fulfilling. “The rewarding aspects of my job are that I am able to follow patients and families through their experience,” Barnhardt said. “I sometimes watch patients improve and go home, never to return again. Other times I see patients during each admission as they transition from being ‘intensive care’ to being ‘acute’ and then going home, only to return in the future. And then there are the other times, where I have developed a wonderful working relationship with a family, having seen them through many obstacles, only to be at a place that is the end. This is a very difficult time, but it means so much to be there with a family through the last steps of hope, through the grief, the loss, and the time of bereavement, knowing that I made a difference, just from being there with them during that time.”

Giving their clients the knowledge and the means to understand and advocate for their needs is another great reward that paediatric social workers cite as being sustaining and energizing. “The greatest reward for me was empowering the patient/family to come to the table with the greatest minds in medicine where they unapologetically demanded what they needed/wanted,” Leger told Online MSW Programs.

REFERENCES

- Amadi, U. (2024). *Counselling in Medical Social Work*. Emu Integrated Services.
- Ayllon, T., & Azrin, N. H. (1968). *The token economy: A motivational system for therapy and rehabilitation*. New York: Appleton-Century--Crafts.
- Bandura, A. T. (1977). *Social learning theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Bandura, A. T., Ross, D., & Ross, S. A. (1963). Imitation of film-mediated aggressive models. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 67, 3—11.
- Bankart, C.P (1997). *Talking cures: A history of Western and Eastern psychotherapies*. Belmont, CA: Books/Cole.
- Bugental, J. F. T. (1976). *The search for existential identity: Patient-therapist dialogues in humanistic psychotherapy*. San Francisco: Jossey—Bass.
- Butler, A. C., Chapman, J. E., Forman, E. M., & Beck, A. T. (2006). The empirical status of cognitive—behavioral therapy: A review of meta-analyses. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 26(1), 17—31.
- Carlson, J., Watts, R. E., & Maniaci, M. (2006). *Adlerian therapy: Theory and practice*. Washington, D.C.: American Psychological Association.
- Clark, A. J. (2002). *Early recollections: Theory and practice in counseling and psychotherapy*. New York: Brunner-Routledge.
- Clarke, J. J. (1992). *In search of Jung*. London: Routledge.
- Cooper, J. O, Heron, T. E., & Heward, W. L. (2007). *Applied behavior analysis* (2nd Ed.).
- Danto, E.A. (2005). *The outcome of psychoanalysis: The hope for a future*. *The psychologist*, 13(12), 620-623.
- De Jong, P., & Berg, I. K. (2002). *Interviewing for solutions* (2nd Ed). Pacific Grove, CA: Brooks/Cole.
- Deming, W. E. (1986). *Out of the crisis*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Center for Advanced Engineering Study.
- Deutsch, D. (1958). Didactic group discussions with mothers in a child guidance setting—A theoretical statement. *Group Psychotherapy*, XI(1), 52—56.
- Ellis, A. (2004). *The road to tolerance: The philosophy of Rational Emotive Behavior Therapy*. Amherst, NY: Prometheus Books.
- Enright, J. B. (1970). *An introduction to Gestalt techniques*. In J. Fagan & I. L. Shepherd (Eds.), *Gestalt therapy now* (pp. 107—124). New York: Harper & Row.
- Furtmuller, C. (1964). *Alfred Adler: A biographical essay*. In H. L. Ansbacher & R. R. Ansbacher (Eds.), *Superiority and social interest: A collection of later writings* (pp. 311—393). Evanston, IL: Northwestern University Press.
- Guterman, J. T. (1996). Reconstructing social constructionism: A response to Albert Ellis. *Journal of Mental Health Counseling*, 18, 29—40.

- Guterman, J. T. (2006). Solution-focused counseling. Alexandria, VA: *American Counseling Association*.
- Haaga, D. A., & Davison, G. C. (1989). *Outcome studies of rational-emotive therapy*. In M. E. Bernard and R. DiGiuseppe (Eds.), *Inside rational-emotive therapy* (pp. 155—
- Johnson, W. R., & Smith, E. W. L. (1997). *Gestalt empty-chair dialogue versus systematic desensitization in the treatment of phobia*. *Gestalt Review*, 1(2), 150—162.
- Jones, S. L. (1988). *A religious critique of behavior therapy*. In W. R. Miller., & J. E.
- Journal of Sociology and Social Work* (2023). *Integration of Spirituality into the Strengths*. New York: Linked Inc.
- Krapp, K. (Ed.). (2005). Beck, Aaron Temkin. *Psychologists and their theories for students* (vol. 1, pp. 67—91). Detroit, MI: Gale Cengage Publishers.
- Lukas, E., & Hirsch, B. Z. (2002). Logotherapy. In F. W. Kaslow, R. F. Massey, & S. D. Massey (Eds.), *Comprehensive handbook of psychotherapy: Interpersonal/humanistic existential* (vol. 3, pp. 333—356). New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- MacDonald, A. J. (1994). Brief therapy in adult psychiatry. *Journal of Family Therapy*, 16, 415—426.
- National Association of Social Workers (2022). *Occupational Guide*. New York: Times Press.
- NCI (2022). *Dictionary of Cancer Terms*. New York: National Cancer Institute. Retrieved 18 November, 2023.
- NCI (2022). Doctor's Surgery Callings English dictionary achieved from the original on 10 February 2018. Retrieved 18 November, 2023.
- Neukrug, E. S. (Ed.). (2015). *The SAGE Encyclopedia of Theory in Counseling and Psychotherapy*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Neukrug, E. S., & Fawcett, R. C. (2010). *Essentials of testing and assessment: A practical guide for counselors, social workers, and psychologists* (2nd ed.). Belmont, CA: Brooks/Cole.
- News Medical of Life Sciences (2023). *Occupational Guide*. New York: Times Press.
- Nielsen, S. L., Johnson, W. B., & Ellis, A. (2001). *Counseling and psychotherapy with religious persons: A rational emotive behavior therapy approach*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Nwankwo O. C. (2005). *Principles and Applications of Behaviour Modification* (Revised Edition). Port Harcourt: Pam Unique Publishers.
- Nwankwo O. C. (2006). *Abnormal Psychology, the Clinical Approach*. Port Harcourt: Pam Unique Publishers.
- Online MSW Programs (2022). Guide to Careers in Social Work / Psychiatric Social Work (Mental Health): Retrieved 10 April, 2024.
- Peterson, T. (2017, October 23). *Mental Health Counseling: How it Works, Benefits, Healthy Place*. Retrieved on 2023, November 12.
- Poister, E., & Polster, M. (1999). *From the radical center: The heart of Gestalt therapy*. Cleveland, Ohio: The Gestalt Institute of Cleveland Press.
- Regis College (2023) Online Masters of Social Work Curriculum: Retrieved 10, December, 2023.
- Regis College (2023). The Mission of Regis College: Retrieved 9, December 2023
- Rogers, C. R., Gendlin, E. T., Kiesler, D. J., & Trnax, C. B. (1967). *The therapeutic relationship and its impact: A study of psychotherapy with schizophrenics*. Madison, WI: University of Wisconsin Press.
- Rosen, E. J., & Weitman, S. F. (2005). *Jewish families: An overview*. In M. McGoldrick, J. Giordano, & N. Garcia-Preto, *Ethnicity and family therapy* (3rd ed., Pp. 667—680). New York: Guilford Press.
- Ross University (2023). *Occupational Guide*. Florida: Linked Inc.
- Sabate E. (2003). *Adherence to long term therapies: evidence for action*. Geneva World Health Organization; [Google scholar]
- Safran, J. D., & Muran, J. C. (2000). *Negotiating the therapeutic alliance: A relational treatment guide*. New York: Guilford.

- Sautter, R. A., & LeBlanc, L. A. (2006). Empirical applications of Skinner's analysis of verbal behaviors with humans. *The Analysis of Verbal Behavior*, 22, 35—48.
- Servicom Unit (2019). *Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)*. Port Harcourt: University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH)
- Social Work License Map (2022). Guide to Careers in Social Work/ Pediatric Social Work: Retrieved 10 April, 2024.
- The New Social Worker (2023). *Elevating Competence in Social Work*. New York: Times Press. New York: Wiley.
- Ulanov, A. B. (1982). *Transference/Countertransference: A Jungian perspective*. In M. Stein (Ed.), *Jungian analysis* (pp. 68—85). La Salle, IL: Open Court Publishing Company.
- United Nations (2023). *Statistical Manual*: New York. Times Press
- Wacker, D. P., Harding, J., Berg, W., Cooper-Brown, L. J., & Barretto, A. (2003). Punishment. In W. O'Donohue, U. J. Fisher, & S. C. Hayes (Eds.), *Cognitive behavior therapy: Applying empirically supported techniques in your practice* (pp. 308—320). Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.
- Walsh, R. A., & McElwain, B. (2002). *Existential psychotherapies*. In D. J. Cain (Ed.). *Humanistic psychotherapies: Handbook of research and practice* (pp. 253—278). Washington, D.C.: American Psychological Association.
- Young-Eisendrath, P., & Dawson, T. (2008). *The Cambridge companion to Jung* (2nd ed.). New York: Cambridge University Press.